

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

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1. Executive summary

The current deliverable is the third Report on Advisory Board (AB) meetings, of four foreseen reports by the end of the project. The first deliverable (D1.2) was submitted on M6 and included the selection of four AB members. The second deliverable (D1.7) was submitted on M14 and reported the incorporation of two more AB members. This deliverable introduces two new members of the RECAP AB and outlines the most essential points discussed during the meetings.

The AB members were initially approached via emails by means of formal invitation to participate on the AB. The AB members were informed in advance about the project's scope, status and progress through informative material that was sent via emails and they were asked for their availability for an interview. The interviews of the AB members were conducted via Internet using WebEx. This deliverable sums up and presents the main points of the interviews and the recommendations that these experts have provided to the project.

Regarding the structure of the current deliverable, Chapter 2 provides the status of the AB before the incorporation of the two additional members, while Chapter 3 presents the changes made on the board from M14 to M28. The meetings held during this period between members of the AB and the RECAP partners are presented in Chapter 4, and finally, some of the most important recommendations of the members of the AB to RECAP and how these recommendations were handled are summarised in Chapter 5. Chapter 6 briefly presents the whole AB up to the present day.

2. Status of the AB up to M14

The following table presents the six persons and organisations that were appointed as members of the AB up to M14.

Previous Advisory Board members

Name	Organisation & Expertise
Prodromos Kalaitzis	Policy consultant in projects on the development of agri-food business and institutional structures
Peter Fane	Principal Consultant at Eurinco, European policy consultants, Agriculture, Rural development and renewable energy
Socrates Socratous	Senior Officer at the Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organisation
Nektarios Chrysoulakis	Director of Research, at the FORTH, Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas
Clement Atzberger	Full Professor and Head of the Institute of Surveying, Remote Sensing and Land Information (IVFL), BOKU University in Vienna, Austria
Alan Matthews	Professor Emeritus of European Agricultural Policy, Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland

3. Update of the AB list

The AB list may be updated throughout the duration of the project in a case an additional need for consultation or any major challenge will occur. Hence, a webinar will be scheduled with all the AB members aiming to inform them about the progress of the project and consult them with regards to major challenges that may occur during the pilot implementation phase.

The RECAP AB is enhanced with 2 more members and a short description of their qualifications is presented below:

Umberto Di Pasquo

communication, legal and public affairs.

Umberto Di Pasquo is a Senior Policy Advisor at Copa-Cogeca, the association of European Farmers and European Agri-Cooperatives. His portfolio covers cooperative policy, legislation and governance. Umberto is Sherpa of the European Commission High-Level Forum for a better functioning of the food supply chain, as well as a member of the European Commission's Experts Sub-Groups on "Digitalisation in the food supply chains", "Internal Market for food" and, "Private labels". He is a lawyer by training, with a Master degree in International law and European Union policies. He has worked for over a decade in many different fields including cooperative finance, payment systems,

Alexandre Morin

Alexandre Morin graduated as an environmental scientist in 2004 (MSc University of Rouen, France) and is a specialist in the field of sustainable agriculture and environmental assessment methods and software, working as project manager (2004-2012) and national scientific network manager (2013-2016). He joined the Chamber of Agriculture of Pays de la Loire in 2016, and he is managing the engagement of the Chamber of Agriculture in European partnerships and projects such as H2020 and Interreg projects, the EIP-Agri network (with a part-time involvement in the EIP-Agri Service Point), and the EIP Agri network at regional level (Operational Groups).

The full list of the AB members can be found in Chapter 6, while short CVs of all members are also provided in the [RECAP platform](#).

4. Meeting Overview

The scope of the AB meetings was to inform AB members about the RECAP project and the challenges the consortium faces, and to offer the RECAP consortium to elicit some initial crucial recommendations for the project's implementation.

Umberto Di Pasquo

The meeting was held among Umberto, Dimitrios Petalios (CREVIS) and Ifigeneia-Maria Tsioutsia (DRAXIS) via WebEx and after the participants were notified, the meeting recording was started.

The meeting was held on 15th of September 2017 and it lasted for approximately 30 minutes. At first, Dimitris welcomed Umberto on board and thanked him for his participation on the AB. Following the presentation of the RECAP project highlighting the problem, the objectives, the main components of the envisioned platform and the key points of its future implementation, more focus was placed on the view of cooperatives, as representatives of farmers, and the use of services provided by RECAP. Moreover, Umberto expressed the Copa Cogeca's interest in such tools that can contribute to the reduction of administrative costs and burdens arise from Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

Alexandre Morin

The meeting was held among Alexandre, Dimitrios Petalios (CREVIS) and Ifigeneia-Maria Tsioutsia (DRAXIS) via WebEx and after the participants were notified, the meeting recording was started.

The meeting was held on 31st of January 2018 and it lasted for approximately one hour. At first, Dimitris welcomed Alexandre on board and thanked him for his participation on the AB. Then Dimitris presented the project highlighting the key points of its future implementation. Moreover, he presented the problem and the objectives of the RECAP project. Following the demonstration of the RECAP platform presenting the main functionalities of the farmer and consultant's profile, more focus was placed on the interest of using such solutions within the day-to-day work of farmers, the Chamber or cooperatives. Finally, Alexandre described the role and activities of the Chamber giving specific focus on its consultancy services to the farmers.

5. Recommendations and actions

Current Recommendations

Name	Recommendations	RECAP actions
Umberto Di Pasquo	Copa Cogeca's interests in tools that contribute to the reduction of administrative costs that arise from CAP.	RECAP offers personalised services to farmers for their better compliance with the CAP environmental standards (remote sensing results, maps, cc rules – checklist, self-assessment, documents upload, work dairy, reminders, auxiliary material, direct communication with PA/ inspectors).
Umberto Di Pasquo	Cooperatives, especially members of Copa Cogeca, use such tools for different usages and RECAP should be a useful tool for cooperative consultants.	RECAP provides the SDK tool for the agricultural consultants in order to stimulate the development of new added value services. Moreover, RECAP dedicated a co-production phase to identify the needs of the agricultural consultants.
Alexandre Morin	RECAP should facilitate the data import about the Cross Compliance environmental standards.	RECAP provides to the users the Greening calculator with which they can check if they are compliant with the greening rules.
Alexandre Morin	When the RECAP platform will be available to the wide public in Europe, there will be some questions of the compatibility of existing systems.	RECAP focuses to the dissemination of the project and provides detailed information regarding the specific components of the platform. RECAP provides to the users an API which is a bridge between the RECAP system and the existing ones.

Previous Recommendations

Name	Recommendations	RECAP actions
Socrates Socratous	RECAP should take into consideration the possible reluctance of the public authorities to use the RECAP platform in the design of the RECAP platform.	RECAP paid a lot of attention to the needs of the public authorities during the user requirements phase. Two consortium partners are PA and were actively involved in the user requirements identification process and during the development of the platform.

Socrates Socratous	RECAP should take into account to develop a user-friendly environment in the design of the RECAP platform due to the lack of technological resources and personnel's technical knowledge in advanced tools.	RECAP provides an e-learning tool that assists users in better understanding and getting familiar with the functionalities of the platform.
Socrates Socratous	RECAP should pilot test the platform in contact with the public authorities.	Two consortium partners are PA and all the pilot partners will involve more relevant stakeholders in order to have better validation results.
Socrates Socratous	RECAP should try to build trust between the platform and the public authorities during the planning procedure and ensure that every information will be exploited in order to build awareness as soon as possible.	One of the main targets of the RECAP project are the PA. PA from different countries have been informed for the RECAP activities via emails. The partner CREVIS has also presented the project to PA from Denmark and Flanders. DRAXIS and NOA presented RECAP in MARS conferences and NMA and OPEKEPE presented the project in Panta Rhei meetings. On the other hand, most of the services provided by RECAP involve many users in the day to day management of the CAP requirements, so increasing awareness significantly.
Socrates Socratous	RECAP should pay more attention to the requirements and development of the platform regarding the public authorities in order to enable them to gain experience and set structure and the procedures that should be followed in the future.	NMA and OPEKEPE, the two PA partners, were constantly involved in the user requirements and development phases and provided the technical team with feedbacks.
Prodromos Kalaitzis	From the early stages of the project, RECAP should be in constant contact with representatives from public authorities, local organisations and unions and try to build trust between the platform and the farmers during either the dissemination or pilot planning procedure.	RECAP is in constant communication with representatives from public authorities, local organisations and unions trying to disseminate the project's value. The dissemination partner, CREVIS, presents the project in different conferences with audience from all the above mentioned groups. In addition RECAP have developed different workshop for users in the pilot phase, ensuring a practical comprehension of the different utilities of the platform.
Prodromos Kalaitzis	RECAP dissemination should start only after the platform is a well prepared product so that RECAP can build trust with users and convince them to use it.	RECAP started the dissemination before the platform development due to the need of more stakeholders for the user requirement phase and the pilot implementation. Only selected users and supervised by RECAP team of advisors,

		were allowed to use the platform during the pilot phase, inviting clearly all of them to take part in a process of validation of a new tool that obviously needed to be refined.
Nektarios Chrysoulakis	RECAP should consider the constraints on the applicability of EO methods due to the spatial resolution of EO data, the crop type, the features of the object that are analysed or on the topography in which the remote sensing is applied.	RECAP took into consideration these constraints and tried to train the algorithm based on these and on the needs of each pilot. Spatial resolution is currently a clear limit for certain uses but we have opened a way of analysis in order to overcome these limits perhaps with complementary tools such as photos.
Nektarios Chrysoulakis	Pilot cases should be focused on one specific area and be established based on the cross-compliance checkpoints that would be specified.	Each pilot case focuses on a specific area of interest and the remote sensing algorithm is trained based on their specific needs and constraints.
Peter Fane	RECAP platform should be integrated to the existing systems of the five pilot countries.	RECAP enables existing systems to connect to RECAP platform through API.
Peter Fane	RECAP platform should be a useful tool for the UK adjustment process in the new agricultural policy	-
Clement Atzberger	RECAP should take into consideration the possibility of a collaboration with JRC.	RECAP has identified some stakeholders in the Monitoring Agricultural Resources (MARS) and several Policy Officers interlinking with the MARS' activities.
Clement Atzberger	RECAP should organise a meeting with JRC in order to discuss EU Policy issues regarding the agricultural sector.	RECAP organised a Policy session during the first review meeting in Brussels and invited members of JRC.
Clement Atzberger	RECAP should involve JRC as soon as possible in order to clarify their expectations and develop a product compliant with the EU regulations.	RECAP has started communication with JRC in order to involve them to the EEAB and keep up with imminent EU Policy adaptations.
Clement Atzberger	RECAP should take into consideration the possibility to collaborate with EODC, which provides EO data.	RECAP may contact EODC in order to establish a connection for future collaboration.
Alan Matthews	RECAP should have specific modules for each of the pilots countries due to the different needs generated from the cross compliance rules. These modules should be easily adapted to existing systems.	RECAP platform was customised for each of the five pilot countries including different software components for some of them.
Alan Matthews	Farmers feels anxious by the risk of making mistakes trying to comply with the regulations.	RECAP platform offers a customised cross compliance rules checklist which is

	<p>RECAP should take into consideration this and be a useful tool for farmers.</p>	<p>created after the farmer has edited the necessary details in his/ her profile.</p>
<p>Alan Matthews</p>	<p>Farmers feels frustrated by the rules complexity and diversity. RECAP should try to simplify the procedure of compliance.</p>	<p>RECAP offers an e-learning component with which farmers are able to watch videos related to the use of RECAP platform, the inspections, and the cross compliance rules. The content of the video is defined from each Paying Agency.</p>

6. List of AB members

Current Advisory Board members

Name	Organisation & Expertise
Prodromos Kalaitzis	Policy consultant in projects on the development of agri-food business and institutional structures
Peter Fane	Principal Consultant at Eurinco, European policy consultants, Agriculture, Rural development and renewable energy
Socrates Socratous	Senior Officer at the Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organisation
Nektarios Chrysoulakis	Director of Research, at the FORTH, Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas
Clement Atzberger	Full Professor and Head of the Institute of Surveying, Remote Sensing and Land Information (IVFL), BOKU University in Vienna, Austria
Alan Matthews	Professor Emeritus of European Agricultural Policy, Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland
Umberto Di Pasquo	Senior Policy Advisor at Copa Cogeca, the association of European Farmers and European Agri-Cooperatives
Alexandre Morin	Manager of the Chamber of the Chamber of Agriculture in European partnerships and projects